

Emotional Stability and Gender : A Study of Orphanage Students in Jammu and Kashmir

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ABSTRACT

Emotional stability is a key element of psychological well-being, determining how individuals cope with stress and emotional difficulties. It refers to the ability of how an individual manages their emotions in stressful situations. Orphans especially those who are residing in orphanages, can face a difficulty in maintaining emotional balance due to the absence of reliable parental support and care and the often-unstable institutional environments. This paper tried to explore the emotional stability of students residing in orphanages of Jammu and Kashmir, paying attention to how gender differences may affect various dimensions of emotional well-being. The findings indicate significant gender-based differences in emotional stability, with male students displaying higher emotional stability in overall and in its five dimensions namely mental health, adaptability, sharing, expression of emotions and worriedness. The researcher has also attempted to provide valuable insights for developing gender-focused initiatives to improve the emotional well-being of orphan children in the region.

Keywords: Emotional Stability, Gender Differences, Orphanage Students, Psychological Well-being

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Introduction:

Emotional stability is a crucial component of psychological well-being, shaping how individuals perceive and connect with their society. Emotional stability plays a central role in shaping how individuals manage their emotional responses to trauma and stress. Its influence goes beyond mental health to influence academic achievement, as emotionally stable individuals are better able to concentrate, form social connections, and cope with the emotional pressures of education.

Emotional stability refers to the ability to manage emotional balance in the midst of challenges. Individuals with emotional stability are capable of managing daily pressures well, maintaining calmness and strength without being overwhelmed by negative emotions such as anxiety, anger, or nervousness. (Mazza et al., 2020).

Emotional stability refers to an individual's ability to keep a stable emotional state, effectively dealing with stress and adapting to new realities. This characteristic allows individuals to face life's challenges with strength and composure. (Chaturvedi and Chander, 2010) For orphans residing in institutional settings, achieving emotional stability can be tough. Research has demonstrated that these children are more prone to behavioural and emotional issues, including anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder. The absence of a reliable and consistent emotional support, often resulting from frequent staff changes and weak caregiver-child bonding, adds to these challenges. Without the nurturing presence of parental figures, orphaned children may face challenges in developing secure attachments, further affecting their emotional well-being.

Research has shown that orphans in institutional care experience distinct and unique psychological and emotional challenges. Maqbool and Jahangir (2022) determined that gender significantly influences the mental health of institutionalized adolescents in Kashmir, with females exhibiting higher emotional instability than males, highlighting that gender influences the experience and expression of emotions.

Bhat (2014) studied emotional stability and depression in orphan students studying in secondary stage. The study found that orphans had lower emotional stability and high level of depression than students with parents, drawing attention to their vulnerability to emotional distress and the necessity for specialised mental health interventions.

Kumar and Singh (2017) studied emotional intelligence in orphan and non- orphan primary school students. Their findings revealed no overall difference, but orphan boys and girls exhibited higher emotional intelligence than their non-orphan counterparts, implying that gender significantly influences emotional intelligence.

This study is of profound relevance as it explores the gender-based variations in emotional stability among orphanage students in Jammu and Kashmir. By exploring dimensions such as mental health, adaptability, sharing behaviours, worriedness, and emotional expression, this study seeks to present comprehensive insights that can shape focussed interventions, ultimately strengthening the emotional well-being. and resilience of both male and female orphans in the region.

Objective:

1. To compare the emotional stability of secondary level students of orphanages of Jammu and Kashmir on the basis of gender
2. To examine gender differences in mental health scores as a dimension of emotional stability among these students.
3. To examine gender differences in adaptability scores as a dimension of emotional stability among these students
4. To find out difference in the score of dimension of sharing of emotional stability on the basis

of gender.

5. To find out difference in the score of worriedness of emotional stability on the basis of gender.
6. To find out difference in the score of Expression of Emotions of emotional stability on the basis of gender.

Hypothesis:

- There is no significant difference in the overall emotional stability scores between male and female secondary-level students in orphanages of Jammu and Kashmir.

- There is no significant difference in mental health scores, as a dimension of emotional stability, between male and female secondary-level students in these orphanages.

- There is no significant difference in adaptability scores, as a dimension of emotional stability, between male and female secondary-level students in these orphanages.

- There is no significant difference in sharing scores, as a dimension of emotional stability, between male and female secondary-level students in these orphanages.

- There is no significant difference in worriedness scores, as a dimension of emotional stability, between male and female secondary-level students in these orphanages.

There is no significant difference in expression of emotions scores, as a dimension of emotional stability, between male and female secondary- level students in these orphanages.

A descriptive research design was adopted to explore the relationship between emotional stability and academic achievement among orphan students of Jammu and Kashmir, particularly those residing in orphanages.

Population :

Population in the present study consists of Secondary class students residing in orphanages of Jammu and Kashmir.

Sample and Sampling Technique:

The study sample consisted of 100 secondary school students from orphanages across Jammu

and Kashmir, selected through stratified random sampling to ensure representation of both genders.

Data Collection Tools:

1. Emotional Stability Rating Scale Data was collected by self-constructed emotional stability scale. The scale has five dimensions: mental health, adaptability, emotional expression, and anxiety levels. It was self-constructed and validated for secondary level students of orphanages.

2. Academic Achievement Records Based on students' grades in their previous examinations.

To assess the difference, with the help of statistical software SPSS, an independent samples t-test was employed with level of significance specified at 5%. *t-test* is a parametric test of difference, used to compare and evaluate the means of two groups to find out if the difference between them is significant. As the data in the current study approximately meet the requirement of meeting the assumptions for a parametric test to be used, *t-test* was used to test the difference. Following is the dimension wise analysis and discussion of the results of the *t-test*:

Table-1
Difference in Emotional Stability of Male and Female Students

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	T	P
Emotional	Male	50	147.70	20.98	4.650	.000*
Stability	Female	50	137.43	23.62		

**p<0.05 level: Significant at 0.05*

Table 4.1 presents the results of a comparison between male and female students in terms of emotional stability. A significant difference in emotional stability scores was found between male and female students. Male students reported higher emotional stability scores (M = 147.70) compared to female students (M = 137.43). As the p-value was less than .05, revealing that the difference was statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, and it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in emotional stability between male and female students with male students demonstrating higher emotional stability than female students.

Table-2
Dimension of Male and Female of Students in Mental Health

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	T	P
Mental	Male	50	35.87	5.12	4.098	.000*
Health	Female	50	31.28	6.03		

**p<0.05 level: Significant at 0.05*

Table-2 presents the results of a comparison between single and double orphans in terms of mental health. A significant difference in mental health scores was found between the two groups. Male students reported higher mental health scores (M = 35.87) compared to female students (M = 31.28). The p-value was less than .05, indicating that the difference was statistically significant. As a result, the null hypothesis is rejected, and it can be determined that there is a significant difference in mental health between male and female students, with male students reporting better mental health than female students.

Table-3**Difference in Emotional Stability of Male and Female Students in the Dimension of Adoptability**

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	t	P
Adaptability	Male	50	34.72	5.58	3.645	.001*
	Female	50	30.94	6.47		

**p<0.05 level: Significant at 0.05*

Table 4.3 displays the comparison of adaptability scores between male and female students. A significant difference was found in adaptability, with male students reporting higher adaptability scores (M = 34.72) compared to their female counterparts. The p-value was less than .05, indicating that the difference was statistically significant. As a result, the null hypothesis was rejected, and it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in adaptability between male and female students, with male students exhibiting higher adaptability.

Table-4**Difference in Emotional Stability of Male and Female Students in the Dimension of Sharing**

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	t	P
Sharing	Male	50	19.45	3.12	3.289	.002*
	Female	50	17.13	4.25		

**p<0.05 level: Significant at 0.05*

Table 4 shows that a significant difference was found in sharing, with male students reporting higher sharing scores (M = 19.45) compared to female students (M = 17.13). The p-value was less than .05, exhibiting that the difference was statistically significant. As a result, the null hypothesis was rejected, and this leads to the conclusion that there is a significant difference in sharing between male and female students, with male students demonstrating higher levels of sharing.

Table-5**Difference in Emotional Stability of Male and Female Students in the Dimension of Expression of Emotions**

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	t	P
Expression of Emotions	Male	50	27.14	4.05	4.852	.000*
	Female	50	24.68	4.90		

**p<0.05 level: Significant at 0.05*

Table 5 presents the comparison of expression of emotions between male and female students. A significant difference was found in expression of emotions, with male students reporting higher scores (M = 27.14) compared to female students. The p-value was less than .05, indicating that the difference was statistically significant. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected, and it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in the expression of emotions between male and female students, with male students exhibiting higher levels of emotional expression.

Table-6**Difference in Emotional Stability of Male and Female Students in the Dimension of Worriedness**

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	t	P
Worriedness	Male	50	30.52	4.83	3.444	.001*
	Female	50	28.41	5.11		

**p<0.05 level: Significant at 0.05*

Table 4.6 shows that a significant difference was found in worriedness, with male students reporting higher levels of dealing with worriedness ($M = 30.52$). As displayed in the table p-value was less than .05, indicating that the difference was statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, and it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in worriedness between male and female students, with male students exhibiting higher levels of dealing with worriedness.

Findings:

- Significant difference was revealed in emotional stability in male and female students, with male students revealing higher emotional stability than female students.
- Significant difference was found in mental health dimension of male and female students, with male students demonstrating higher emotional stability than female students.
- Significant difference was present in adaptability dimension of male and female students, with male students demonstrating higher emotional stability than female students
- Significant difference was found in sharing dimension of male and female students, with male students exhibiting higher emotional stability than female students
- Significant difference was found in expression of emotions dimension of male and female students, with male students showing higher emotional stability than female students
- Significant difference was found in worriedness dimension of male and female students, with male students revealing higher emotional stability than female students

Educational Implication:

The findings of this study have important educational implications for orphan students residing in orphanages. The significant differences in emotional stability, mental health, adaptability, sharing, expression of emotions, and worriedness between male and female students indicate the requirement of gender-focussed strategies in the emotional and psychological support systems within

orphanages. Taking into account that male students showed higher emotional stability across these dimensions, it is important to develop individualized programs that address the specific emotional needs of female students, who may face greater emotional challenges. Teaching strategies should concentrate on promoting emotional strength, psychological stability, and adaptability in both genders, giving priority to enhancing the emotional expression and coping mechanisms of female students. In addition, integrating counselling services, social skills training, social interaction development and peer support systems could assist in bridging the emotional gaps between male and female students, promoting a more balanced, nurturing and supportive environment for all orphan children.

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